

Software-defined control for sliceable multi-dimensional optical networks

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Abstract:

Space-division multiplexing (SDM) transmission technology is attracting attention as an upcoming technology for ultra-large capacity optical networks. In this presentation, we will review the current research and development status of control technology for SDM optical networks. In addition, we will report several demonstrations of software-defined control for sliceable SDM optical networks.

Acknowledgements

This work was partially supported by "Massive Parallel and Sliced Optical Network", NICT, JAPAN and EC H2020 BLUESPACE (762055) project.

Biography:

Noboru Yoshikane (Ph.D.) joined KDD Corporation. (currently KDDI Corporation), Tokyo, Japan in 1999, and since 2001 he has been working at their research and development laboratories. He is currently a R&D manager of the photonic transport network laboratory of KDDI Research. He has been engaged in a wide range of R&D topics including design of submarine cable systems, terrestrial transport network systems, designing and modeling of photonic networks, disaster resilient/robust network architecture, OTN, SDN/NFV, network control/management and orchestration, disaggregated optical network systems, and 5G transport networks.